

Physico-Chemical Study on the Beryllium Complexes of Methyl-3-Mercaptopropionate

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Complex formation of beryllium (Be^{2+}) ion with methyl-3-mercaptopropionate, $\text{CH}_3\text{OOCCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{SH}$, has been studied in 25% ethanolic media by potentiometric and conductometric techniques. Two complexes 1 : 1, 1 : 2 are formed in the pH range 4.1-6.5 whose $\log K_{\text{stab}}$ values, determined at ionic strength 0.1M (KNO_3) by employing Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method and various other alternative methods, are 4.23, 3.29 at 25°; 4.06, 3.17 at 35° and 3.83, 3.04 at 45° respectively. The overall changes in thermodynamic function ΔG , ΔH , ΔS accompanying complexation reactions are evaluated at 35° and are -10.19 Kcal/mole, -14.45 Kcal/mole and -13.83 Cal/deg/mole respectively.

THIOLS are very useful from biological, pharmaceutical and analytical points of view. These act as strong complexing agents due to the presence of active -SH group. Several metal complexes of thiols have already been studied by Saxena and co-workers¹⁻³. The present communication reports the composition of the Be^{2+} : methyl-3-mercaptopropionate complexes, their stability constants evaluated by employing Calvin Melchior extension of Bjerrum's method and several other alternative methods viz., method of successive approximation, convergence formula, least square method; and overall changes in free energy, enthalpy, entropy accompanying the complexation reactions. There is, however, no reference in the literature on the present investigations.

Experimental

Methyl-3-mercaptopropionate (referred to herein as RSH) was obtained from Evan's Chemetics, Inc., New York and the other chemicals used were of Anal-R (BDH) quality. pH measurements were made on a Cambridge Bench pattern pH meter with glass-calomel electrode assembly. Conductance was measured on an electronic eye-type conductometer. The experimental procedure as described earlier¹, involved a series of pH and conductometric titrations of RSH in absence and presence of Be^{2+} ion against standard NaOH.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry :

For establishing the stoichiometry of the complex species formed during the interaction of Be^{2+} and RSH, the magnitude of the proton displacement was determined by titrating the solution containing RSH and Be^{2+} in different molar ratios against standard alkali.

The sudden rise in pH on the addition of NaOH to the ligand (Fig. 1, curve 1) indicates that the

proton of -SH group is not titrable under the experimental conditions. The addition of an equimolar concentration of Be^{2+} ion greatly alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve (Fig. 1, curve 4)

Fig. 1. pH titrations of the solutions.
(1) 4.0 mM RSH, (2) 4.0 mM RSH + 1 mM BeSO_4 ,
(3) 4.0 mM RSM + 2.0 mM BeSO_4 , (4) 4.0 mM RSH + 4.0 mM BeSO_4 against 0.1M NaOH.

indicating the complex formation which results in the lowering of the buffer region due to the proton displacements.

Since the extent of proton displacement depends on the relative affinity of ligand for H^+ and the metal ion, it is obvious from the curve that the interaction of Be^{2+} ion with RSH is sufficient to compete with a relatively high concentration of hydrogen ions. The appearance of a precipitate and inflection at $m = 2$ suggests the decomposition of $\text{Be}(\text{RS})^+$ in accordance with the following equation

With the metal and the ligand in the ratio 1 : 2 and 1 : 4, the inflection is obtained at $m = 1, 0.5$ respectively (Fig. 1, curve 3, 2) which confirms the above conclusions.

Conductometric titrations of RSH in absence and presence of Be^{2+} ion, mixed in different ratios, against standard NaOH yield breaks in curves corresponding to the formation of $\text{Be}(\text{RS})_2$ as obtained from $p\text{H}$ titrations.

Stability constants :

The stability constants of the complexes have been calculated from Bjerrum's method⁴ as extended by Calvin and Melchior⁵. The reaction equilibria may be represented by the following expressions :

The overall stability constant β is given by

$$\beta = \frac{[\text{Be}(\text{RS})_2]}{[\text{Be}^{2+}][\text{RS}^-]^2} = K_1 K_2 \quad \dots (6)$$

where K_1, K_2 are the formation constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes.

The $p\text{H}$ titrations of RSH in absence and presence of Be^{2+} ions in $\mu = 0.1M$ (KNO_3) were carried out at 25°, 35° and 45° (Fig. 2). At any $p\text{H}$, the ratio

Fig. 2. $p\text{H}$ titrations of RSH in absence and presence of Be^{2+} Ions with 0.1M NaOH.

Curves a, b, c : 8 mM RSH + 0.1M KNO_3 + 0.005M HClO_4 at 25°, 35° and 45° respectively.

Curves a', b', c' : 8 mM RSH + 0.1M KNO_3 + 0.005M HClO_4 + 1 mM of Be^{2+} at 25°, 35° and 45° respectively.

of the horizontal distance between the resulting curves to the total concentration of the metal ions gives the formation function \bar{n} . Concentration of free ligand $[\text{A}]$ at various $p\text{H}$ values have been calculated from the relation

$$[\text{A}] = \frac{[\text{RSH}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{Be RS}^+] - 2[\text{Be}(\text{RS})_2]}{\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_a} + 1} \quad \dots (7)$$

where K_a , the dissociation constant of RSH determined by polarographic method⁶, is 1.12×10^{-10} .

Formation curves are obtained by plotting \bar{n} vs. $-\log[\text{A}]$ (Fig. 3). The values of $\log K_1, \log K_2$

Fig. 3. Formation curves at (1) 25°, (2) 35° and (3) 45°.

were read directly from these curves at $\bar{n} = 0.5, 1.5$ respectively which were further refined by the following methods :

1. Schroder's convergence formula⁷;
2. Solving the successive equations derived from Bjerrum's formation function⁴.

$$\sum_{n=0}^N (n - \bar{n}) [\text{A}]^n \beta_n = 0.$$

3. Least square method.⁸

The $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values obtained by different methods are almost similar varying within a range of 3% and are given in Table 1.

Thermodynamic Functions :

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS), accompanying complexation, have been determined at 35° with the help of standard equations⁹.

The value of ΔG obtained from the expression $\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta$, is -10.19 Kcal/mole.

ΔH was determined with the help of an isobar

equation $\frac{d \ln \beta}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2}$ which may be rewritten as

$$\frac{d(\log \beta)}{d\left(\frac{1}{T}\right)} = -\frac{\Delta H}{4.57}$$

The values of $\log \beta$ obtained at different temperatures were plotted as a function of $1/T$. The

TABLE I.—VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS DETERMINED BY VARIOUS METHODS AT 25°, 35° AND 45°.

Methods	25°			35°			45°		
	log K_1	log K_2	log β	log K_1	log K_2	log β	log K_1	log K_2	log β
Bjerrum's method	4.33	3.23	7.56	4.15	3.10	7.25	3.93	2.97	6.90
Successive approx. method	4.24	3.32	7.56	4.05	3.20	7.25	3.81	3.09	6.90
Convergence Formula	4.21	3.35	7.56	4.10	3.24	7.34	3.88	3.14	7.02
Least Square Method	4.15	3.29	7.44	3.95	3.14	7.09	3.71	2.95	6.66

gradient of the tangent drawn at the point corresponding to 35° was determined and equated to $-\frac{\Delta H}{4.57}$. The value of ΔH thus obtained was found to be -14.45 Kcal/mole. ΔS was then evaluated from the relation

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

and found to be -13.83 Cals/deg/mole.

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